

**A mathematical approach to
optimizing magnesium
carbonate (MgCo_3) to maximize
friction coefficient in rock
climbing**

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Introduction & Rationale

Magnesium carbonate (MgCO_3), also known as chalk, is a synthetic form of carbonated sedimentary rock designed to give rock climbers a better grip, reduced palm sweat, and better friction between the hands and climbing holds (Science, Geology). As a climber for the Brazilian national team, I constantly rely on chalk to provide me with the most friction during practice and competitions. Moreover, it appears that I often tend to sweat more on my palms, which increases my need to use climbing chalk even further. However, I have always wondered whether the use of this substance actually leads to a significant impact on grip while climbing (Science, Geology). Some climbers feel that too much chalk actually reduces friction, whereas others see chalk as a rather unnecessary tool and, therefore, no considerable advantage in its use (Climbing Way). There is currently insufficient evidence proving the efficacy of climbing chalk in increased friction (Myers). This is because many variables such as temperature, texture, and skin moisture come into play to determine whether chalk is, in fact, crucial for a climber's friction. Therefore, only I can determine whether chalk significantly impacts my performance as an athlete.

Upon hearing of an opportunity to explore this mathematically, I figured that understanding the mechanisms of friction and calculating it at different wall inclinations would provide significant insight into the efficacy of chalk in my climbs. This led me to the research question: **What is the relationship between climbing chalk (MgCO_3) and increased friction coefficient (μ_i) at variable surface inclination?** To answer this question, two hypotheses were proposed:

Null Hypothesis (H_0) - There is no significant difference between climbing chalk ($MgCO_3$) and increased friction coefficient at a variable surface inclination.

Alternate Hypothesis (H_1) - There is a significant difference between climbing chalk ($MgCO_3$) and increased friction coefficient at a variable surface inclination.

Aim

The primary aim of this investigation is to determine whether chalk is a significant factor in increased friction while climbing. This can be beneficial for my climbing competitions, as I will be able to maximize hand-hold friction and increase my chances of finishing a climb without slippage. For this, the coefficient of friction, which is explained later in the investigation, will be calculated on a curved handhold surface that is attached to a self-inclining climbing wall. Further, I will utilize geometry, specifically the length of arcs to review preliminary trials. For data processing, I will use statistical tests and determine the statistical difference between the data obtained in two distinct conditions (chalk vs no chalk). The results presented in this study are solely based on my own data to evaluate and recognize the efficacy of climbing chalk on my performance as an athlete.

Background Information

Part of my training involves using an electronic climbing board (Kilterboard®) to create my own climbing problems. The Kilterboard contains more than 300 hand holds with various shapes to promote thorough finger strength activation. To carry out this investigation, I will utilize one climbing hold in particular

Figure 1: Kilterboard app 12x12 board (Screenshot)

(see figure 1). This hold is commonly known by the climbing community as a 'sloper' due to its slippery surface that demands a significant amount of body tension and friction to be hung from. Additionally, the board itself has a variable surface inclination, meaning I can adjust its angle automatically. Theoretically, the steeper the angle, the harder it is to hang off a climbing hold. The combination of a sloper with a variable surface will be an essential determinant of the efficacy of chalk in this study.

Friction Coefficient

Friction is referred to as the resistance encountered by a body when moving over another. The concept of friction is commonly measured through the friction coefficient. Essentially, two distinct forces are generated when two surfaces come into contact. The first is the perpendicular force, or else known as the normal force (N). It prevents solid objects from going through one another. Moreover, the

tangential force (F) is the force that “opposes relative movement between two surfaces” (Sivamani et al.). The concept is originally derived from Amonton's law, stating that the instantaneous coefficient of friction (μ_i) is found by calculating the ratio between the tangential and normal force (Desplanques):

$$\mu_i = \frac{F}{N}$$

The coefficient of instantaneous friction, however, is not related to static or dynamic friction coefficients since the μ_i is directly reliant on a change in time. Therefore, the μ_i is most suitable for this study as it usually occurs before slippage (Fuss and Niegl).

Figure 2: Visual Representation of the Physics of Friction(Author’s Own)

Normal Force

The normal force is commonly shown as perpendicular to the surface. Therefore, it is the force exerted when hanging off the climbing hold surface, preventing the hand to pass through it (Khan Academy):

$$F_N = mg\cos\theta$$

Where F_N is the normal force,

m is the mass of a sliding object,

g is the acceleration due to gravity,

and θ is the inclination angle.

Tangential force

The tangential force on the other hand will stand perpendicular to the normal force and is in this context, a result of the inclining wall (Richefeu and Villard):

$$F_t = mgsin\theta$$

Where F_t is the normal force,

m is the mass of a sliding object,

g is the acceleration due to gravity,

and θ is the inclination angle.

Slope of inclination

The initial setup must first be designed before data can be collected. Preliminary trials were conducted to address the experimental setup as well as the initial slope of the wall. Though angle identifications are present in figure 3, they contain a large degree of reading uncertainty. For more accurate data collection, a digital inclinometer (Spirit Level, $\pm 0.2^\circ$) was used to measure each trial's initial and

final angles. Because of the limited inclination levels of the Kilterboard (ranging between ≈ 26.5 and 70°), the initial angle had to be established at 30° .

Figure 3: Expected Experimental Setup (Authors own)

On the press of a button, the wall inclines by a constant, unknown velocity. Identifying the velocity is crucial in determining the validity of the investigation because additional factors such as time elapsed and endurance levels account for accurate data collection (Völker). This means the velocity must be high enough to allow the wall to sufficiently incline before slippage due to friction, rather than slippage by lack of endurance. To calculate the velocity of inclination, the following equation is used:

$$\text{Average Velocity} = \frac{\text{Change in } \theta (\Delta\theta)}{\text{Change in Time}(\Delta T)}$$

To calculate the Kilterboard's inclination velocity, a sample test was performed to identify the time taken for the wall to incline 10° . The time taken for the wall to incline from 30 to 40° was 28.86 seconds, measured using the Stopwatch app on the phone (± 0.005 seconds). Further, the dimensions of the wall were also measured

using a measuring tape (Stanley FatMax, ± 0.05 cm), and a value of 3.66 x 3.66 meters was found. Three significant figures were used for this measurement, as two decimal places are provided by the measuring tape.

Figure 4: Visual Representation of Section of Circumference(10°) (Author's own)

The method involves finding the arc length created by the change in inclination of the wall. This is because the arc length reveals the total distance traveled by the Kilterboard after inclining 10° .

To find the arc length of a circumference, the following formula is used:

$$\text{Arc Length} = 2\pi r \left(\frac{\theta}{360} \right)$$

Where r is the radius of the wall. In this situation, the radius = length, therefore $r = 3.66\text{m}$, and θ is the difference between the final and initial angle created by the inclined wall (10°).

By inputting the obtained values into the equation, we get:

$$\text{Arc Length} = 2(3.14)(3.66) \left(\frac{10}{360} \right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = (6.28)(3.66) \left(\frac{10}{360} \right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = (22.9848)\left(\frac{10}{360}\right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = \left(\frac{229.848}{360}\right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = 0.638\text{m}$$

Knowing the distance traveled by the Kilterboard was 0.638m in 28.86 seconds, it can be shown that the average distance traveled per second is:

$$X = \frac{0.638}{28.86}$$

$$X = 0.0221\text{m/s}$$

Hence, the Kilterboard moves at a distance of 0.0221m/s or else 0.347°/s. In order to determine how much of the total inclination this value actually accounts for, the maximum slope will be analyzed.

Looking at the maximum Kilterboard slope in figure 5, it is seen that the Kilterboard is able to move 2.55m in its totality:

Figure 5: Visual Representation of Section of Circumference(40°)(Author's own)

$$\text{Arc Length} = 2(3.14)(3.66)\left(\frac{40}{360}\right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = \left(\frac{919.392}{360}\right)$$

$$\text{Arc Length} = 2.55\text{m}$$

If the wall is able to move 2.55m at 0.0221m/s, a preliminary trial that inclines 10° will account for 25.02% of the maximum Kilterboard distance:

$$\left(\frac{0.638}{2.55}\right) \times 100 = 25.02\%$$

It can be concluded from the preliminary trials that about one-quarter of the total Kilterboard inclination is used for one trial. This means, the final distance traveled is not a result of endurance, but rather due to loss of friction, which is what the investigation aims to achieve. Hence, the use of the Kilterboard's velocity is a viable method and will allow for an attempt in answering the research question.

Methodology

Experimental Protocol

I will hang off the hold with straight arms in a natural position for a total of 18 trials divided into 9 using climbing chalk, and 9 without (see figure 3). The grip used is a slope grip technique: using four fingers, the thumb is not used to apply any counterforce. The wall will start inclining once I do not have any direct support with the feet. For this, someone will need to be pressing onto a button that will trigger the inclination process. Time is elapsed from when the wall starts inclining until I slip from the hold. However, the trial is repeated if I change the grip test position at any moment during data collection. When I slip from the hold, a 5 minutes rest is given before the next trial. This is done to avoid any result deviation due to muscle exhaustion. After each trial, the hold is cleaned with a brush to thoroughly differentiate between chalk and no chalk conditions. Moreover, when switching to no chalk conditions, the hands must be washed and dried to prevent any moisture.

* The initial angle of the wall is measured using the electronic gyroscope sensor. Angular displacement is recorded with a video camera (Apple Ipad pro) at a 60Hz sample rate.

Analytical Protocol

The slippage angle is measured by the final angle for each trial. Next, the coefficient of friction(CoF) is defined by analyzing the frame representing the exact slippage point. “It consists of the ratio between tangential force and normal force” (Sivamani et al.). Data is collected and analyzed separately to determine the CoF of each trial.

Statistical Protocol

The mean value, standard deviation, and standard error of all 9 trials in chalk and no chalk conditions are reviewed for statistical analysis. Those are the three major components to conduct the ANOVA one-way test, a statistical test utilized to analyze any statistical difference between two or more groups or data. The analysis of variance will be used to address whether the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected by comparing the means of chalk and no chalk trials. A categorical independent variable (chalk vs non-chalk) and a quantitative dependent variable (coefficient of friction) are used. Therefore, the ANOVA one-way test is the most appropriate tool to analyze the relationship between those.

Coefficient of Instantaneous Friction

Data Collection

9 trials was conducted for each of the different chalk conditions. The slippage angle was recorded and placed in table 1 (see appendix A).

The normal and tangential force can be calculated at each specific slippage angle from table 1:

$$F_N = mg\cos\theta$$

Where F_N is the normal force,

$$m = 60.8\text{kg (body weight)}$$

The acceleration due to gravity (g) is treated as 9.81 m/s^2

and $\theta = 40.25$

$$F_N = (60.8)(9.81)\cos(40.25)$$

$$F_N = (596.448)\cos(40.25)$$

$$F_N = 455.2$$

$$F_t = mg\sin\theta$$

Where F_t is the tangential force,

$$m = 60.8\text{kg (body weight)}$$

The acceleration due to gravity (g) is treated as 9.81 m/s^2

and $\theta = 40.25$

$$F_t = mg\sin\theta$$

$$F_t = (60.8)(9.81)\sin(40.25)$$

$$F_t = (596.448)\sin(40.25)$$

$$F_t = 385.4$$

The CoF can now be found by dividing the tangential force by the normal force:

$$\mu_i = \frac{385.4}{455.2}$$

$$\mu_i = 0.85$$

The process is repeated for all slippage angles obtained in this study. Table 2 below shows the processed CoF values:

Table 2: Calculated coefficient of friction in with/without chalk conditions

Trial Number	Normal Force		Tangential Force		Coefficient of Friction	
	Chalk	No Chalk	Chalk	No Chalk	Chalk	No Chalk
1	455.2	492.4	385.4	336.5	0.85	0.68
2	463.5	484.7	375.4	347.6	0.81	0.72
3	455.2	486.2	385.4	345.5	0.85	0.71
4	449.5	492.1	392.1	337.0	0.87	0.68
5	466.8	490.7	371.3	339.1	0.80	0.69
6	467.4	490.4	370.5	339.5	0.79	0.69
7	457.6	492.7	382.6	336.1	0.84	0.68
8	458.6	490.1	381.4	340.0	0.83	0.69
9	457.6	481.6	382.6	351.8	0.84	0.73

Data Processing

The mean, standard deviation, and standard error are now calculated to show the spread of data obtained in this study. The formula used to calculate the mean is shown below:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Where \bar{X} is the mean,

$\sum X$ is the sum of all values collected, and

n is the total number of data values

To calculate the mean CoF for chalk and no chalk conditions:

\bar{X} is the mean CoF **with** chalk.

$\sum X$ is the sum of all 9 values.

n is set to 9.

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{X} &= \frac{0.85+0.81+0.85+0.87+0.80+0.79+0.84+0.83+0.84}{9} \\ \bar{X} &= \frac{7.47}{9} \\ \bar{X} &= 0.8311\end{aligned}$$

\bar{X}' is the mean CoF **without** chalk

$\sum X$ is the sum of all 9 values

n is set to 9

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{X}' &= \frac{0.68+0.72+0.71+0.68+0.69+0.69+0.68+0.69+0.73}{9} \\ \bar{X}' &= \frac{6.29}{9} \\ \bar{X}' &= 0.6967\end{aligned}$$

The sample standard deviation is found using the following formula:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

Where s is the sample standard deviation,

\bar{x} is the mean obtained beforehand,

x_i is a value from the data set,

$\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2$ is the summation of the difference

between x and \bar{x} squared, and

n is the total number of data values.

To calculate the standard deviation of the CoF for chalk and no chalk conditions:

s is the standard deviation **with** chalk,

$$\bar{x} = 0.83$$

x is a value from the data set,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - 0.83)^2 \text{ and}$$

n is 9 data values

$$(0.85 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.81 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.85 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.87 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0016$$

$$(0.80 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0009$$

$$(0.79 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0016$$

$$(0.84 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$(0.83 - 0.83)^2 = 0$$

$$(0.84 - 0.83)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$0.0004 + 0.0004 + 0.0004 + 0.0016 + 0.0009 + 0.0016 + 0.0001 + 0 + 0.0001 = 0.0055$$

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{0.0055}{9-1}}$$

$$s = \sqrt{0.000686}$$

$$s = 0.0262$$

s' is the standard deviation **without** chalk,

$$\bar{x} = 0.70$$

x is a value from the data set,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - 0.70)^2 \text{ and}$$

n is 9 data values

$$(0.68 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.72 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.71 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$(0.68 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.69 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$(0.69 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$(0.68 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0004$$

$$(0.69 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0001$$

$$(0.73 - 0.70)^2 = 0.0009$$

$$0.0004 + 0.0004 + 0.0001 + 0.0004 + 0.0001 + 0.0001 + 0.0004 + 0.0001 + 0.0009 = 0.0029$$

$$s' = \sqrt{\frac{0.0029}{9-1}}$$

$$s' = \sqrt{0.000363}$$

$$s' = 0.0187$$

The standard error is found using the following formula:

$$SE_{\bar{x}} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Where $SE_{\bar{x}}$ is the standard error,

s is the sample standard deviation calculated beforehand, and

n is sample size

To calculate the standard error of the CoF for chalk and no chalk conditions:

SE_x is the standard deviation **with** chalk,

$$SE_x = \frac{0.0262}{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$SE_x = 0.0087$$

SE'_x is the standard deviation **without** chalk,

$$SE'_x = \frac{0.0191}{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$SE'_x = 0.0062$$

Figure 6: Bar graph showing the mean coefficient of friction and standard deviation between chalk and no chalk conditions

Statistical Analysis

A significant statistical difference will be represented by a p-value lower than its critical value ($p = 0.05$). Conducting the Anova one-way test revealed that the p-value obtained was 0.

Table 3: Processed Data Summary

Chalk Condition	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error
Chalk	9	0.8311	0.0262	0.0087
No Chalk	9	0.6967	0.0187	0.0062

*For all statistical analysis calculations, all values are taken 4 decimal places into account

Table 4: Formulas for One-way ANOVA of independent treatments (Good Calculators)

Source	Degrees of Freedom (DF)	Sum of Squares (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	F-Stat	P-Value
Between Groups	$k - 1$	SS_B	$MS_B = SS_B / (k - 1)$	$F = MS_B / MS_W$	$F(k-1, N-k)$
Within Groups	$N - k$	SS_W	$MS_W = SS_W / (N - k)$		
Total	$N - 1$	$SS_T = SS_B + SS_W$			

Degrees of Freedom (DF)

Between Groups

$$DF = k - 1$$

Where k is the number of groups

$$DF = 2 - 1$$

$$DF = 1$$

Within Groups

$$DF = N - k$$

Where N the total subject number

$$DF = 18 - 2$$

$$DF = 16$$

Total DF

$$DF = N - 1$$

$$DF = 18 - 1$$

$$DF = 17$$

Sum of Squares (SS)

Between Groups

$$SS_B = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2$$

Where n_i is the number of subjects in the i-th group, \bar{x}_i is the mean of the i-th group and \bar{x} is the grand mean.

$$SS_B = 9[(0.8311 - 0.7639)^2 + (0.6967 - 0.7639)^2]$$

$$SS_B = 9[0.00451584 + 0.00451584]$$

$$SS_B = 9[11.2338]$$

$$SS_B = 0.0813$$

Within Groups

$$SS_W = \sum_{i=1}^k (n_i - 1) S_i^2$$

Where S_i is the standard deviation of the i-th group.

$$SS_W = (9 - 1)0.0262^2 + (9 - 1)0.0187^2$$

$$SS_W = (8)0.0262^2 + (8)0.0187^2$$

$$SS_W = 0.0083$$

Total SS

$$\begin{aligned}SS_T &= SS_B + SS_W \\SS_T &= 0.0813 + 0.0083 \\SS_T &= 0.0896\end{aligned}$$

Mean Square (MS)

Between Groups

$$\begin{aligned}MS_B &= \frac{SS_B}{(k-1)} \\MS_B &= \frac{0.0813}{(2-1)} \\MS_B &= 0.0813\end{aligned}$$

Withing Groups

$$\begin{aligned}MS_W &= \frac{SS_W}{(N-k)} \\MS_W &= \frac{0.0083}{(18-2)} \\MS_W &= 0.0005\end{aligned}$$

F-Statistic

$$\begin{aligned}F &= \frac{MS_B}{MS_W} \\F &= \frac{0.0813}{0.0005} \\F &= 156.9014\end{aligned}$$

P-Value

A TI-84 Plus Graphic Display Calculator is used to conduct a Right-tailed test to find the P-Value. The function tcdf (2ND, VARS (DISTR), tcdf) is utilized where:

tcdf(smaller value, larger value, degrees of freedom)

* The F-Statistic value (156.9014) can be used as the smaller value, 9999 as the larger, and 17 as the total degrees of freedom: (see appendix B)

The P-Value obtained was = 1.28839292E-28 and will therefore be rounded to 0.

The values obtained can now be placed in the ANOVA one-way table for analysis (see table 5):

Table 5: One-way ANOVA of independent treatments

Source	Degrees of Freedom (DF)	Sum of Squares (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	F-Stat	P-Value
Between Groups	1	0.0813	0.0813	156.9014	0
Within Groups	16	0.0083	0.0005		
Total	17	0.0896			

It can be concluded that from the One-way ANOVA test, the p-value is < 0.05 , proposing that there is a significant statistical difference between my independent treatments. Hence, this study's Null Hypothesis(H_0) - **There is no significant difference between climbing chalk ($MgCO_3$) and increased friction coefficient at variable surface inclination** can be rejected.

Analysis

Overall, the mean CoF ranged from 0.68 to 0.85. The mean CoF with chalk was 0.83 ± 0.03 , whilst the mean CoF without chalk was 0.70 ± 0.02 . Through the One-way ANOVA, it is found that chalk has a significant effect on CoF, shown by a p-value < 0.05 . Moreover, chalk had an 18.6% positive effect on increased CoF ($\frac{(0.83 - 0.70)}{0.70} \times 100$) allowing me to grip onto the climbing hold for an additional 4.74° on average. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) - **There is a significant difference between climbing chalk ($MgCO_3$) and increased friction coefficient at a variable surface inclination** is supported.

Evaluation

The ease of conducting the study is undoubtedly one of the strengths. All required is access to a Kilterboard, and having such a device allows not only the implementation of this study but a range of explorations on how to maximize friction when climbing. Additionally, this study can be conducted safely as there are no apparent ethical, environmental, or physical issues if handled appropriately. For instance, having mattresses on the floor comforts and ensures a safe landing. This is essential in providing safety and allowing many trials to be done without the potential

risk of injury. Further, the addition of statistical tests aided the analysis of the results mathematically. The ANOVA test provided significant insights into the statistical relevance since the initial data obtained showed minor differences at first glance, allowing for a more thorough evaluation of the two independent treatments. Moreover, the GDC allowed a different approach to finding the final P-Value with its built-in function 'tcdf' which would otherwise require a longer process to calculate.

Table 6: Evaluation of Limitations, Impact on Study, and Suggestion for Improvement

Limitation	Effect on Study	Suggestion for Improvement
Supplementary subject required for the performance of the study.	Someone knowledgeable about the concept and device is needed to be consulted beforehand. This is because someone must constantly press a button to incline the Kilterboard. Therefore, the study had to be split into different days, which could have led to a slight change in the data collected due to variable health and strength levels.	Finding a subject willing to perform the study in one direct predetermined period of time.
Limited data samples	9 trials resulted in significantly small standard deviations (see figure 6), which can contribute to a more problematic data analysis and interpretation.	Increase in the number of trials and participants, allowing for a greater dispersion of a dataset in relation to its mean.
Swing during trial	Swinging the body when hanging is an inevitable consequence of starting the trial at an already inclined angle. This is certainly able to generate ambiguous data, as the swing can be higher or lower depending on the initial body's position.	This limitation could be further investigated and taken as one additional variable. However, I am limited in applying mathematics to this concept by not taking physics as one of my IB subjects.

Conclusion

The study was targeted to examine the effects of chalk on the coefficient of friction between a curved handhold surface and a climber's hand utilizing variable surface inclinations. An innovative method was proposed to calculate the coefficient of friction using an electronic climbing board. The design enabled the visualization of hold-finger friction from a variety of angles and how chalk plays a big role in assisting a climber in overhang scenarios. The major result of this study shows a significant effect of chalk in positively affecting the coefficient of friction. Furthermore, the results now allow me to recognize that my performance in the sport is also heavily influenced by whether or not I am applying chalk to my hands, which plays a big role when it comes to competitions where I should be aware of situations where chalk enhances the friction between my hands and curved handholds.

Suggestion for Further Investigation

Though the investigation only explored one determinant of the coefficient of friction, it may be extended to a temperature or texture-induced analysis. For instance, the investigation can further explore friction within different hand temperatures and/or textures like wood or limestone. Moreover, an even larger cohort with varied climbing abilities could be studied in order to reach a more holistic outcome of the effectiveness of chalk in a community. The Kilterboard can still be used to investigate both suggestions proposed.

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Appendix A

Table 1: Raw data collected for with/without chalk slippage angles

Trial number (n)	Chalk (°)	No Chalk(°)
1	40.25	34.35
2	39.00	35.65
3	40.25	35.40
4	41.10	34.40
5	38.50	34.65
6	38.40	34.70
7	39.90	34.30
8	39.75	34.75
9	39.90	36.15
Mean	39.67	34.93

Appendix B

GDC used to find P-value with tcdf tool:

The TCDF (Student's t cumulative distribution function) tool on the GDC calculates the probability of getting a value less than or equal to a specified t-score, given the degrees of freedom, using the Student's t-distribution.

The result is the area under the t-distribution curve, which is the P-value.

